

REINFORCEMENT LEARNING FOR DYNAMIC PUMP SCHEDULING UNDER DEMAND UNCERTAINTY

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ABSTRACT

Reliable and cost-efficient scheduling of pumps is an important task in the daily operations of urban water distribution networks (WDNs). In this work, we address the scheduling of variable-speed pumps using reinforcement learning (RL), which allows network controls to adapt to changes in demand in real-time after a data-driven training phase. Previous contributions have shown the general suitability of RL for control tasks in WDNs [1], [2]. However, most of them assume deterministically known demand patterns (cf. [1]) or consider uncertainty only for valve control (cf. [2]). As RL algorithms can handle uncertain environments, we explore their potential for dynamic scheduling of the network's pumps under uncertain demand patterns. Our optimisation goal is to train a policy that complies with upper and lower pressure bounds at all nodes in the network while minimising the cost of pumping. To this end, we make use of the Soft Actor-Critic algorithm (SAC) [3]. Data for training and testing is collected using the EPANET simulator for two benchmark networks (Net1 and Anytown) with uncertainties applied to various network parameters. In all setups, the controller is trained without nodal demand information. Our study shows promising results for a pump scheduler that can reduce energy cost by a significant amount while complying with pressure bounds even for unseen scenarios.

Keywords: Reinforcement Learning, Pump Scheduling, Demand Uncertainty

1. INTRODUCTION

Efficient control of pumps is a crucial task for water utility operators worldwide, as the cost of pumping constitutes the largest part of their expenses [4].

Adapting the pumps to fluctuations in the demands offers considerable energy savings over a fixed schedule. With growing availability of sensor devices, increased efforts have been made throughout the last decade to tackle the dynamic pump scheduling problem with Reinforcement Learning [1], [5], [6].

This work proposes an approach based on the Soft Actor Critic algorithm [3] for the control of variable-speed pumps in uncertain scenarios. Section 1.1 introduces Reinforcement Learning and SAC. In Section 1.2, we discuss related work in the field of RL-applications for network control. Section 2 describes our problem formulation in detail. Results for the two benchmark networks are discussed in Section 3. Finally, Section 4 provides a concluding summary and an outlook on future work.

1.1 REINFORCEMENT LEARNING AND SOFT ACTOR CRITIC

Figure 1. Agent-Environment-Model in Reinforcement Learning, copied from [7]

Reinforcement Learning is a branch of Machine Learning that considers an agent trying to find optimal actions in an unknown environment. At each discrete time step t the agent observes the current state S_t and takes an action A_t . In return, it receives a scalar reward signal R_{t+1} from the environment, which then transitions to a new state S_{t+1} . The transition itself is governed by a probability distribution $P(r, s' | s, a)$ which describes the dynamics of the environment and is typically not known to the agent. The overall goal is to find a policy, i.e., a probability distribution over actions given the state (typically denoted as $\pi(a | s)$), such that its expected cumulative reward is maximized by actions taken, which were sampled from the policy. The interaction between agent and environment is schematically shown in Figure 1. For tasks that can be naturally decomposed into episodes, like games with a fixed end-state, this interaction is repeated for a finite number of T timesteps. For an in-depth introduction to Reinforcement Learning, including illustrative examples as well as underlying math, we refer the interested reader to [7].

Among many algorithms proposed to solve RL problems, SAC [3] is particularly appealing for the control of multiple variable-speed pumps in WDNs for two main reasons: First, the use of a replay buffer allows for efficient utilisation of data collected during previous episodes, reducing the time for extensive simulations. Second, the objective optimised in SAC not only encourages high reward actions, but also policies with high entropy during training, leading to a better exploration of feasible solutions and more robust results. Finally, SAC tackles problems with a continuous action space, which renders it suitable for a fine-grained control of variable speed pumps. A rigorous formalisation of the algorithm, including mathematical guarantees, can be found in the original paper [3].

1.2 RELATED WORK

Existing methods in the field can be differentiated by the objectives they aim to fulfil with their schedule and by the type of scheduling they address. Objectives typically include minimization of cost or energy consumption [4]. However, a wide range of additional objectives is considered in the literature, including robustness to leakage events [8], control of tank water levels [9] and satisfaction of pressure bounds at consumer nodes [1]. Our approach takes pressure bounds and energy consumption into account. In order to prevent damage to the pump, we introduce an additional term to facilitate a smooth transition between speed settings that mitigates frequent switches.

In our review of existing literature, we encountered fixed and dynamic schedules, as well as binary, discrete and continuous approaches: Publications treating the scheduling problem as part of water network design typically

employ a fixed schedule which is determined as part of the design optimization [10]. Dynamic scheduling approaches aim to adapt their schedule with varying conditions of the network: While some approaches are designed to turn pumps on or off [5], others use a fixed increment or decrement of speed at each time step [1] or determine the speed as a continuous variable [6]. Our approach addresses the continuous setting to improve adaptation to small fluctuations. Multiple recent approaches rely on RL for an optimized scheduling [1], [6], [11]. In most of these, demand patterns are assumed to be fixed or completely known and passed to the RL agent as part of the current state. However, neither a fixed demand nor accurate demand measurements at every household can be assumed in practice. Therefore, we train our agent without knowledge of demands based on sensor measurements across the network (see problem definition below). To test the generalisation ability of the agent, we conduct experiments with uncertain demand patterns as well as additional uncertain network parameters in the case of the LeakDB benchmark. A recent paper by Pei et al [6] presents the most closely related approach, also taking demand uncertainty into account. Our contribution extends their approach in three key aspects: (1) We evaluate the agent's performance under uncertain network parameters like pipe lengths and diameters for LeakDB; (2) Our problem formulation incorporates an upper bound for node-level pressure to mitigate leakage risk; and (3) Instead of Proximal Policy Optimization [12] we rely on SAC.

2 PROBLEM DEFINITION AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The agent executes an action by choosing relative speed settings between 0 and 1 every 30 minutes for all pumps in the network. The state observed by the agent is composed of pressure readings, flow readings at the inlet and at tank connections, tank levels, pump energy consumption and the current time of day. To adapt to the smoothness reward (see below), we add the three previously chosen speed settings to the observation space. In LeakDB, we use pressure readings at all network junctions. To make our experiments more realistic in terms of sensor data availability, we choose a subset of 8 junctions at random for Anytown and use pressure data only from these. Information about normalisation and encoding of observations can be found in the Supplementary Material.

After each action, the next environment state is computed using the EPANET simulator through the EPyT-Flow Python library [13]. The reward signal is computed based on the resulting network state as a weighted sum of partial rewards:

$$R_{total} = c_1 \cdot R_{pressure} + c_2 \cdot R_{energy} + c_3 \cdot R_{smoothness} - 0.5$$

$$s. t. \quad c_1 + c_2 + c_3 = 1, \quad c_1, c_2, c_3 < 1$$

All partial rewards are scaled to lie between 0 and 1. We subtract 0.5 to centre the reward around zero, which has empirically shown to have good effects on the training process. The most important partial reward is given by the nodal pressure bounds:

$$R_{pressure} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbb{I}(h_{min} < h[n] < h_{max}).$$

It measures the agent's ability to satisfy the lower and upper pressure bounds h_{min} , h_{max} at N consumer nodes, where \mathbb{I} is the indicator function and $h[n]$ is the pressure at node n .

The second partial reward contains the energy consumption

$$R_{energy} = 1 - \sum_{p=1}^P \frac{E(p)}{E_{max}(p)},$$

For P pumps, where $E(p)$ is the energy consumption of pump p and $E_{max}(p)$ is its maximum energy consumption, determined empirically before optimization. The curvature of a pump's speed setting over time is approximated by

$$\kappa_{p,t} = |(v_{p,t-2} - v_{p,t-1}) - (v_{p,t-1} - v_{p,t})|$$

where $v_{p,t}$ is the relative speed setting of pump p at time t .

In order to penalise high curvature, or equivalently, to incentivise a smooth transition of speed settings, we use the following smoothness reward:

$$R_{smoothness} = 1 - \frac{1}{P} \sum_{p=1}^P \min(\kappa_{p,t}, 1)$$

where P is the total number of pumps. Note the clipping of individual curvature values, which is applied to scale the reward between 0 and 1.

In all our presented experiments, the reward weights are fixed to $c_1=0.87$, $c_2=0.1$, $c_3=0.03$. We use the SAC implementation of Stable Baselines 3 (see Supplementary Material for the hyperparameters). Following the general guidelines for pressure constraints in water networks [14] and the original formulation of the Anytown benchmark [15], we use a lower pressure constraint of 28.12m (40 PSI) and an upper constraint of 70m. Due to stochasticity, we repeat training 5 times with different seeds for SAC on each benchmark.

LeakDB: This benchmark [16] consists of multiple scenarios for Net1, differing in pipe lengths, pipe diameters, roughness coefficients and demands. On each episode, we run a different scenario for 7 days. Tests were conducted on a scenario not seen during training.

Anytown: We run 24-hour simulations on a modified network version, derived from Reis et al [17]. The demand pattern is multiplied by a factor sampled from a normal distribution with a mean of 1 and a standard deviation of 0.05 before the start of each episode. The distribution is truncated at [0.7, 1.3] to avoid extreme outliers. In addition, the demand multiplier of the pattern at each node is perturbed by up to 5%. To account for this uncertainty, the results for Anytown reported below in Table 1 are additionally averaged over ten 24-hour episodes obtained from actions of the fully trained agents.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of our experiments are summarised in Table 1. We compare our approach to an optimised constant baseline on both networks and to a Genetic Algorithm (GA) on Anytown. The constant baseline is obtained using a simple grid search. The GA is applied to a simplified binary pump scheduling problem for Anytown: Each gene represents the number of active pumps, and a solution consists of one gene for each control timestep. Hyperparameters for the GA can be found in the Supplementary Notes.

The results show that our RL-based scheduler can save a considerable amount of energy in comparison with existing approaches. At the same time, it learned to reliably comply with pressure bounds, ensuring safe network operations. Note that the reported pressure bound violations for LeakDB can be fully explained by an overfilled tank leading to high pressures at the beginning of each scenario. After this initial violation, the constraints are permanently met.

Table 1. Performance of a dynamic pump scheduler trained with Reinforcement Learning compared to baseline approaches. For Anytown, both baselines are optimised for a worst-case scenario (demand pattern multiplied by 1.3) to make sure that there is a sufficient supply for peak demands. The table contains mean values and standard deviation in parentheses over ten episodes and 5 experiment repetitions with different seeds.

Experiment	Pressure [%]	Energy [MWh]	Smoothness [%]
Anytown (Constant)	99.7(0.1)	29.756(0.740)	98.7(0.1)
Anytown (GA)	97.3(0.5)	27.803(0.981)	59.9(0.0)
Anytown (RL, 8 Sensors)	100 (0.0)	22.622 (1.151)	95.9 (1.1)
LeakDB (Constant)	95.2	6.026	100.0
LeakDB (RL)	95.5 (0.0)	4.366(0.420)	99.0(0.0)

4 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we have used a Reinforcement Learning approach for the dynamic scheduling of pumps in Water Distribution Networks. To this end, we have used the Soft Actor Critic algorithm [3], which is known for robust learning in continuous action spaces. In our optimisation, we have focused on the reduction of energy consumption and compliance with pressure constraints. The comparison to existing approaches for fixed schedules shows that our method has the potential for considerable savings in energy while ensuring compliance with pressure bounds.

In our future work, we plan to extend the objective function, e.g., by including tank level restrictions. Furthermore, in the spirit of Safe-RL and transferability to the real world, we plan to investigate and avoid the exploration of unsafe states, including states which trigger EPANET warnings. Furthermore, based on these promising results for two small WDN benchmarks, we aim to extend the application to larger and more challenging networks.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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REFERENCES

- [1] G. Hajgató, G. Paál, and B. Gyires-Tóth, 'Deep Reinforcement Learning for Real-Time Optimization of Pumps in Water Distribution Systems', *J. Water Resour. Plan. Manag.*, vol. 146, no. 11, p. 04020079, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1061/(ASCE)WR.1943-5452.0001287.
- [2] A. Belfadil, D. Modesto, J. Meseguer, B. Joseph-Duran, D. Saporta, and J. A. Martin Hernandez, 'Leveraging Deep Reinforcement Learning for Water Distribution Systems with Large Action Spaces and Uncertainties: DRL-EPANET for Pressure Control', *J. Water Resour. Plan. Manag.*, vol. 150, no. 2, p. 04023076, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.1061/JWRMD5.WRENG-6108.
- [3] T. Haarnoja, A. Zhou, P. Abbeel, and S. Levine, 'Soft Actor-Critic: Off-Policy Maximum Entropy Deep Reinforcement Learning with a Stochastic Actor', in *PMLR*, Aug. 2018, pp. 1861–1870. Accessed: Feb. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v80/haarnoja18b>

- [4] H. Mala-Jetmarova, N. Sultanova, and D. Savic, 'Lost in optimisation of water distribution systems? A literature review of system operation', *Environ. Model. Softw.*, vol. 93, pp. 209–254, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.envsoft.2017.02.009.
- [5] A. Candelieri, R. Perego, and F. Archetti, 'Intelligent Pump Scheduling Optimization in Water Distribution Networks', in *Learning and Intelligent Optimization*, vol. 11353, R. Battiti, M. Brunato, I. Kotsireas, and P. M. Pardalos, Eds., in Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 11353, Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 352–369. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-05348-2_30.
- [6] S. Pei, L. Hoang, G. Fu, and D. Butler, 'Real-Time Pump Scheduling in Water Distribution Networks Using Deep Reinforcement Learning', *J. Water Resour. Plan. Manag.*, vol. 151, no. 6, p. 04025012, Jun. 2025, doi: 10.1061/JWRMD5.WRENG-6476.
- [7] R. Sutton and A. Barto, *Reinforcement Learning - An Introduction*, 2nd ed. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press, 2018.
- [8] O. Giustolisi, D. Laucelli, and L. Berardi, 'Operational Optimization: Water Losses versus Energy Costs', *J. Hydraul. Eng.*, vol. 139, no. 4, pp. 410–423, Apr. 2013, doi: 10.1061/(ASCE)HY.1943-7900.0000681.
- [9] B. Barán, C. Von Lücken, and A. Sotelo, 'Multi-objective pump scheduling optimisation using evolutionary strategies', *Adv. Eng. Softw.*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 39–47, Jan. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.advengsoft.2004.03.012.
- [10] A. Ostfeld and A. Tubaltzev, 'Ant Colony Optimization for Least-Cost Design and Operation of Pumping Water Distribution Systems', *J. Water Resour. Plan. Manag.*, vol. 134, no. 2, pp. 107–118, Mar. 2008, doi: 10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9496(2008)134:2(107).
- [11] J. Xu, H. Wang, J. Rao, and J. Wang, 'Zone scheduling optimization of pumps in water distribution networks with deep reinforcement learning and knowledge-assisted learning', *Soft Comput.*, vol. 25, no. 23, pp. 14757–14767, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s00500-021-06177-3.
- [12] J. Schulman, F. Wolski, P. Dhariwal, A. Radford, and O. Klimov, 'Proximal Policy Optimization Algorithms', Aug. 28, 2017, arXiv:1707.06347. Accessed: Jun. 13, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1707.06347>
- [13] A. Artelt, M. S. Kyriakou, S. G. Vrachimis, D. G. Eliades, B. Hammer, and M. M. Polycarpou, 'EPyT-Flow: A Toolkit for Generating Water Distribution Network Data', *J. Open Source Softw.*, vol. 9, no. 103, p. 7104, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.21105/joss.07104.
- [14] V. Ghorbanian, B. Karney, and Y. Guo, 'Pressure Standards in Water Distribution Systems: Reflection on Current Practice with Consideration of Some Unresolved Issues', *J. Water Resour. Plan. Manag.*, vol. 142, no. 8, p. 04016023, Aug. 2016, doi: 10.1061/(ASCE)WR.1943-5452.0000665.
- [15] T. M. Walski *et al.*, 'Battle of the Network Models: Epilogue', *J. Water Resour. Plan. Manag.*, vol. 113, no. 2, pp. 191–203, Mar. 1987, doi: 10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9496(1987)113:2(191).
- [16] S. G. Authors: Vrachimis, 'LeakDB: a Benchmark Dataset for Leakage Diagnosis in Water Distribution Networks: (146)', *WDSA CCWI Jt. Conf. Proc.*, vol. 1, Jul. 2018, Accessed: Jan. 17, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://ojs.library.queensu.ca/index.php/wdsa-ccw/article/view/12315>
- [17] A. L. Reis, A. Andrade-Campos, C. Henggeler Antunes, M. A. R. Lopes, and A. Antunes, 'Cost-Efficient Pump Operation in Water Supply Systems Considering Demand-Side Management', *J. Water Resour. Plan. Manag.*, vol. 150, no. 6, p. 04024017, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.1061/JWRMD5.WRENG-6215.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

To improve training stability, we normalized some parts of the observation space. Pressure readings were linearly rescaled such that a scaled measurement of 0 corresponded to the lower pressure bound and a scaled measurement of 1 corresponded to the upper bound. Flow measurements were divided by a maximum flow, determined empirically before training. Tank level readings were linearly rescaled to a range of 0 (minimum tank level) to 1 (maximum tank level). The time of day was represented with two values between -1 and 1 using an angular encoding:

$$d_1(t) = \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T}\right), \quad d_2(t) = \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T}\right), \quad T = 24h.$$

For SAC, we used the default hyperparameters of Stable Baselines 3 with two exceptions: We increased the learning rate to 3×10^{-3} and fixed the entropy coefficient to 10^{-2} .

Hyperparameters for the GA are given in the table below. The remaining parameters were taken from the default settings of the PyGAD library.¹

Parameter	Value
number of generations	125
solutions per population	20
number of parents mating	6
gene space	[0, maximum number of pumps]
number of genes in a solution	number of time steps

Data Availability Statement: Code and data can be found under the following link: https://github.com/HammerLabML/RL4Water_CCWI2025

¹ <https://pygad.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>